

GL MICAVE

D5.5 GLOMICAVE pre-operational consolidated platform - "beta" release

Project ref. no.	Horizon 2020-NMBP-TR-IND-2020 GA No. 952908
Project title	Global Omic Data Integration on Animal, Vegetal and Environment Sectors
Duration of the project	1 st November 2020 - 30 th April 2024 (42 months)
WP/Task:	WP5: Big Data platform backend integration and data exploitation / Task 5.6: Agile iterative and continuous integration and deployment for the industrial evaluation
Document due Date:	30/04/2024
Actual date of delivery	01/05/2024
Leader of this deliverable	TREE
Type	Demo
Dissemination level	PUBLIC
Document status	Submitted

Deliverable Information sheet

Version	Date	Author	Document history/approvals
0.1	24/03/2024	TREE	Draft version circulated to partners
0.2	29/04/2024	EUT	Contributions added
1.0	30/04/2024	EUT	Final document

Executive summary

This document provides an overview of the consolidated demo version of the integrative approach of the GLOMICAVE pre-operational consolidated platform including guidelines of installation. The content of this document is the result of several interactions between the technical and end-users' partners, providing a final version of the GLOMICAVE platform.

As a result, a pre-operational consolidated version of the GLOMICAVE platform has been made available for the consortium.

GLOMICAVE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 952908.

This document is the sole responsibility of the consortium and reflects only the consortium view. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains and can in no way be taken to reflect the views of the European Union.

Table of contents

List of figures	4
1. Introduction	5
2. GLOMICAVE platform	5
2.0 Overview data platform	5
2.1 FRONT END.....	5
2.2 Execution process framework	6
2.3 CI/CD.....	6
2.4 Knowledge Graph databases	6
3. Workflow description	6
4. Conclusion.....	13

List of figures

Figure 1. Workflow schema and correspondence in the main site	7
Figure 2. Data exploration interface	8
Figure 3. Publications containing a specific metabolite (serine) and a specific gene (ETR1)	9
Figure 4. Details on the specific papers	10
Figure 5. Data uploading page	10
Figure 6. List of all data available and uploaded by the user	11
Figure 7. New Project creation panel	11
Figure 8. Metadata check to ensure consistency	11
Figure 9. User projects (Jobs) list.....	12
Figure 10. Results list.....	12

1. Introduction

This outcome starts at the early stages of the development phase and following an agile approach, was in charge of coordinating the integration of the different components (backend components; frontend and API) in-line with the defined integration methodology and integration environment.

General practices for continuous integration/continuous deployment were applied, following a continuous, iterative, incremental integration approach, since the early stages to the final consolidation of the pre-operational platform. Therefore, this task implies the coordination and execution of continuous integration of the components during all stages, from early prototypes and non-operative mock-up-components to the final pre-operational consolidated GLOMICAVE platform. The pre-operational GLOMICAVE platform resulting from this task has been released together with guidelines for its instantiation to support the industrial validation in the different industrial cases.

2. GLOMICAVE platform

2.0 Overview data platform

The GLOMICAVE platform seeks to implement a robust cloud-based data platform designed to integrate and analyse large omics datasets in diverse areas such as agriculture, livestock, and environment. It relies on Big Data technologies and advanced analytics to process and extract valuable information from vast repositories of genomic and phenomic data.

The architecture provides a system that facilitates the execution of processes for the predictive analysis and deep understanding of biological systems and the identification of genotype-phenotype relationships.

2.1 FRONT END

- **GRAPH QUERIES**

The main platform's knowledge graph (KG) is composed of a relational database. Users can query this KG using the front-end query assistant. To that end, a back-end strategy to query the databases using was developed.

Queries were designed using the specific schema structures of the data. As part of the development process, the execution speed – to minimize user's waiting time to ensure a near real-time query system - was tested and benchmarked and optimised the scalability and resource utilization, using specific optimization techniques such as index utilization.

- **BACKEND-FRONT-END INTEGRATION.**

The integration between the back-end and front-end has been implemented following a microservices architecture, with each microservice specializing in a specific function. The primary interactions between the backend and frontend focus on providing responses to user queries against the databases and executing jobs using the datasets uploaded by users on the platform. Regarding graph management, a request redirection policy has been defined for queries against databases, always aiming to obtain query results quickly.

Concerning project management, coordination is implemented for uploading user datasets. Once datasets are uploaded, users have the option to create projects by configuring various parameters such as algorithm type, organism, and additional parameters. The main algorithm is a pathway inference algorithm, which can be integrated with two additional algorithms. Each algorithm runs independently, ensuring platform fault tolerance.

- **VISUALIZATION GRAPHS**

A graphical visualization using networks graphs has been developed to generate graphs for pathway representation as well as for correlation information on omics entities. To that end, visual representations of biological pathways were generated to assist users in the interpretation of complex relationships within pathways.

The core of the visualization script involves binding the visual elements enabling dynamic updates as needed. Nodes and edges are represented and extended capabilities were implemented including

tooltips, zooming, and node highlighting, enhancing the user experience and facilitating deeper exploration of the pathway network.

Throughout the development process, attention was paid to performance optimisation to ensure smooth rendering and interaction, particularly for large-scale pathway networks.

2.2 Execution process framework

- **BACKEND API**

The back-end of GLOMICAVE architecture is designed to efficiently handle the processing of incoming data. A pod is in charge of processing the incoming data, operating within a controlled and scalable environment.

The storage of the inference data is done in an repository, which is essential for storing large volumes of data securely and allowing efficient access to it during the inference process. This repository is crucial for extracting the necessary information from the data model.

On the other hand, a process invokes the necessary models and graphs, passing the inference data through the established systems and managing the execution of different processes sequentially or in parallel as needed to optimise workflow and resource utilisation.

Finally, a storage infrastructure is vital to support advanced analytical operations and ensure that information is consistently and reliably available for decision-making and analytical processes.

2.3 CI/CD

The GLOMICAVE platform is based on the use of git as a code repository manager that provides version control for software development projects.

The GLOMICAVE platform uses GitLab CI/CD as a continuous integration and deployment tool that automates the building, testing and deployment of software for a GitLab code repository. In turn, GitLab CI/CD makes use of GitLab Runners which are agents that run jobs defined in GitLab CI/CD pipelines and allow to distribute the workload in a distributed manner.

2.4 Knowledge Graph databases

The GLOMICAVE platform is oriented to structure and process the information to later store it in graph databases to allow users to represent and manipulate data efficiently, facilitating complex analysis and visualisation of relationships of large datasets.

3. Workflow description

The workflow to use the platform involve three main modules, which can be used independently or in combination either programmatically or by using interrelated queries by the user (Figure 1). These modules include data exploration, literature search and multi-omics integration, and can be accessed via the main platform page.

Figure 1. Workflow schema and correspondence in the main site

- **Data exploration**

Data can be queried using the graphical user interface in the platform, to obtain a graph of correlated elements together with their degree of correlation shown in a graphical manner (Figure 2).

Explore data

Term

SMEL4.1_03g010400.1.01

Is a

Transcript

⌵

Organism

solanum_melongena^x

⌵

View Graph

Start Nodes	Weights	End Nodes
SMEL4.1_03g010400.1.01	0.804	SMEL4.1_08g016590.1.01
SMEL4.1_03g010400.1.01	0.807	SMEL4.1_09g024960.1.01
SMEL4.1_03g010400.1.01	0.811	SMEL4.1_09g018850.1.01
SMEL4.1_03g010400.1.01	0.829	SMEL4.1_06g002700.1.01
SMEL4.1_03g010400.1.01	0.802	SMEL4.1_10g025340.1.01
SMEL4.1_03g010400.1.01	0.815	SMEL4.1_10g023770.1.01
SMEL4.1_03g010400.1.01	0.815	SMEL4.1_12g001890.1.01
SMEL4.1_03g010400.1.01	0.802	SMEL4.1_02g030300.1.01
SMEL4.1_03g010400.1.01	0.819	SMEL4.1_02g022210.1.01
SMEL4.1_03g010400.1.01	0.803	SMEL4.1_02g014370.1.01
SMEL4.1_03g010400.1.01	0.815	SMEL4.1_03g023290.1.01
SMEL4.1_03g010400.1.01	0.806	SMEL4.1_03g022800.1.01
SMEL4.1_03g010400.1.01	0.807	SMEL4.1_04g009980.1.01
SMEL4.1_03g010400.1.01	0.86	SMEL4.1_05g000920.1.01
SMEL4.1_03g010400.1.01	0.859	SMEL4.1_05g018420.1.01
SMEL4.1_03g010400.1.01	0.812	SMEL4.1_06g018380.1.01
SMEL4.1_03g010400.1.01	0.809	SMEL4.1_06g028570.1.01
SMEL4.1_03g010400.1.01	0.82	SMEL4.1_09g002270.1.01
SMEL4.1_03g010400.1.01	0.815	SMEL4.1_01g020450.1.01
SMEL4.1_03g010400.1.01	0.81	SMEL4.1_01g002820.1.01

Figure 2. Data exploration interface, where a specific transcript is searched and the relationship graph is shown

• **Literature search**

The KG containing literature relationships among omics data can be queried through its dedicated user interface, allowing different items to be queried and specific searches be made (Figure 3 and 4).

The screenshot shows the 'Basic Search' interface with the following search criteria:

- Term: serine (Is a: Small molecule)
- Term: ETR1 (Is a: Gene)
- Find: Publication
- Specific term: Term name (Is a: Any type)

Results are displayed as a table with 3 total entries:

Score	Found terms	Publications	Related terms
2	serine,ETR1	1	serine (1) Shoot Development (1) C (1) Threonine (1) NR (1)
1	serine	10	serine (10) Metabolite (4) Amino acid (4) protein (4) amino acids (4)
1	ETR1	9	Ethylene (9) ETR1 (9) Receptor (7) protein (4) Senescence (3)

Figure 3. Publications containing a specific metabolite (serine) and a specific gene (ETR1) are searched. Results show that one paper contains the two terms, while other papers mention one or the other. Co-occurring terms are also shown (Related terms)

Show entries | 1 total entries (1 pages)

PUBLICATION
Terms found: 2

Title LeCTR2, a CTR1-like protein kinase from tomato, plays a role in ethylene signalling, development and defence

DOI 10.1111/j.1365-313X.2008.03481.x

Authors Zhefeng Lin; Lucille Alexander; R. Hackett; D. Grierson

Abstract Arabidopsis AtCTR1 is a Raf-like protein kinase that interacts with **ETR1** and ERS and negatively regulates ethylene responses. In tomato, several CTR1-like proteins could perform this role. We have characterized LeCTR2, which has similarity to AtCTR1 and also to EDR1, a CTR1-like Arabidopsis protein involved in defence and stress responses. Protein-protein interactions between LeCTR2 and six tomato ethylene receptors indicated that LeCTR2 interacts preferentially with the subfamily II **ETR1**-type ethylene receptors LeETR1 and LeETR2, but not the NR receptor or the subfamily II receptors LeETR4, LeETR5 and LeETR6. The C-terminus of LeCTR2 possesses **serine**/threonine kinase activity and is capable of auto-phosphorylation and phosphorylation of myelin basic protein in vitro. Overexpression of the LeCTR2 N-terminus in tomato resulted in altered growth habit, including reduced stature, loss of apical dominance, highly branched inflorescences and fruit trusses, indeterminate shoots in place of determinate flowers, and prolific adventitious shoot development from the rachis or rachillae of the leaves. Expression of the ethylene-responsive genes E4 and chitinase B was upregulated in transgenic plants, but ethylene production and the level of mRNA for the ethylene biosynthetic gene ACO1 was unaffected. The leaves and fruit of transgenic plants also displayed enhanced susceptibility to infection by the fungal pathogen Botrytis cinerea, which was associated with much stronger induction of pathogenesis-related genes such as PR1b1 and chitinase B compared with the wild-type. The results suggest that LeCTR2 plays a role in ethylene signalling, development and defence, probably through its interactions with the **ETR1**-type ethylene receptors of subfamily I.

[See less](#)

Evidences

Publication link

Related Gene Products & Metabolites (32)

Publication link

[EC-CODES/EC.3.2.1.14](#) [NLE-BIO-KG/ACO1](#) [NLE-BIO-KG/MBP](#) [WP/https://identifiers.org/chebi/CHEBI:15356](#)
[WP/https://identifiers.org/chebi/CHEBI:15927](#) [WP/https://identifiers.org/chebi/CHEBI:17822](#)
[WP/https://identifiers.org/chebi/CHEBI:33384](#) [WP/https://identifiers.org/chebi/CHEBI:36080](#)
[WP/https://identifiers.org/chebi/CHEBI:57926](#) [WP/https://identifiers.org/ensembl/AT1G66340](#)

Figure 4. Details on the specific papers where the items are found are shown, highlighting the searched terms within the text

• Multi-omics integration

Multi-omics data from users can be integrated via the GLOMICAVE platform. First, users can easily upload the data into the platform (Figure 5) and check all the data already available to them (Figure 6). Next, a project can be created (Figure 7), its metadata checked to ensure consistency (Figure 8) and a list with all the projects and their current status is also shown (Figure 9). Finally, results can be retrieved (Figure 10).

Search
Explore
Projects
Datasets
Organisms
Users
Joan ▾
Bugs
Datasets

Drag and drop files or click

(Admitted formats: csv, tsv, xls, xlsx)

Name	Type	Size	Progress	Actions
metaboT6_1.csv	text/csv	0.444 MB	<div style="width: 100%; height: 10px; background-color: #ccc;"></div>	Remove
proteoT6_1.csv	text/csv	0.256 MB	<div style="width: 100%; height: 10px; background-color: #ccc;"></div>	Remove

Return
Upload all
Cancel all
Remove all

Figure 5. Data uploading page. An intuitive drag-and-drop system was implemented

Showing 1-16 of 16 datasets

[Clear selection](#) [Remove selected](#) [Upload Datasets](#)

It is kindly recommended to label each dataset with its type

<input type="checkbox"/>	Name	Description	Date	Size	Type	Actions
<input type="checkbox"/>	metaDataPD60_T6_liv3_update.csv		30-04-2024	2 KB	METADATA	Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	Test 30 April_misa_results.xlsx		30-04-2024	20 KB	MISA_RESULTS	Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	Test_misa_results.xlsx		30-04-2024	20 KB	MISA_RESULTS	Edit Delete

Figure 6. List of all data available and uploaded by the user

New project

Name*

Organisms*
 Unspecified
 Acetobacterium woodii
 Anopheles gambiae
 Arabidopsis thaliana
 Bacillus subtilis
 Beta vulgaris

Datasets*

Main phenotype or disease*

Metadata*

[Create](#) [Next \(Check Metadata\)](#) [Cancel](#)

Figure 7. New Project creation panel. The different sections allow users to select the parameters and different organisms of interest

New project | Check Metadata

Please, check if the samples belong to the correct group. Double-click to modify a cell.

[Back](#) [Create Project](#) [Reset Values](#)

Sample ID	Group
2	no
4	yes
6	yes
8	no

Figure 8. Metadata check to ensure consistency. Users are allowed to edit the metadata online

Showing 1-5 of 7 projects

[Clear selection](#)
[Remove selected](#)
[+ New Project](#)

(*) If one project turns to a 'Running' permanent state, please verify your file format by checking the templates in the section 'Fetch Datasets'.

(*) If the problem still persists, please verify whether all the datasets have been assigned a type.

If none of the ways are working, please contact 'adria.olomi@eurecat.org'.

<input type="checkbox"/>	Name	Description	Status	Actions
<input type="checkbox"/>	Test 30 April		Ready	▶ 👁 ✎ 🗑 ⌵
<input type="checkbox"/>	T6_1v3		Running	▶ 👁 ✎ 🗑 ⌵
<input type="checkbox"/>	T6_1_v2		Completed	▶ 👁 ✎ 🗑 ⌵
<input type="checkbox"/>	T6_4		Completed	▶ 👁 ✎ 🗑 ⌵
<input type="checkbox"/>	T6_1		Completed	▶ 👁 ✎ 🗑 ⌵

« « 1 2 » »

Figure 9. User projects (Jobs) list. The page provided information about the project status and allow users to edit and remove the projects

T6_4 ✔ Completed

Created by: d04dd67e-6517-4f47-aebe-3fdc11e8b5e

Created on: 4/26/24, 10:13 AM

Edited on: 4/28/24, 1:28 PM

Datasets: [Transcriptomics_6_4.csv](#)

Organism: mesc

Phenotype / Disease: Stress

Task Output:

[✎ Edit](#)
[▶ Start](#)
[🗑 Delete](#)

Pathways (3)

Pathway id	Name	Organism	Genes number	Metabolites number	P-Value	P-Value-Mat
mesc00071	Fatty acid degradation	Manihot esculenta (cassava)	0	0	0.03	0.0344312392822933
mesc00130	Ubiquinone and other terpenoid-quinone biosynthesis	Manihot esculenta (cassava)	0	0	0.04	0.0406831688972876
mesc00592	alpha-Linolenic acid metabolism	Manihot esculenta (cassava)	0	0	0.01	0.00549273514979784

Figure 10. Results list. Users can visually inspect pathways by clicking on the specific pathway of interest

4. Conclusion

A report on the technical improvements and efforts made to provide a pre-operational consolidated platform (beta release), including both back and front-end improvements, with a focus on improving the visualization and interactivity for an enhanced user experience. A demonstration of the platform workflow is included, showing the different modules implemented within the platform.

The utilization of AWS resources ensures the agility, responsiveness, and resource efficiency necessary for orchestrating GLOMICAVE effectively. The implementation of the Open APIs results in the creation of various endpoints tailored for different interpreters, facilitating data querying. This enhancement significantly improves the user experience, enabling users to query data using their preferred syntax. Moreover, it fosters collaboration within the GLOMICAVE ecosystem, providing a seamless and efficient means of interacting with genomic data.